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Deliverable D5.6
Summary of ongoing international activities

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D5.6 - Summary of ongoing international activities

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¹ **Nature:** R -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** **PU** -Public; **CO** -Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Abbreviations

ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers
CRP	Coordinated Research Project
DELISA-LTO	Description of the Extended Lifetime and its Influence on the Safety Operation and Construction Materials Performance – Long Term Operation with no Compromises in the Safety
EAC	Environmentally Assisted Cracking
ENTENTE	European Database for Multiscale Modelling of Radiation Damage
ETE	Embrittlement Trend Equations
FEM	Finite Element Modelling
FRACTESUS	Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
INCEFA-SCALE	INcreasing safety in NPPs by Covering gaps in Environmental Fatigue Assessment - focusing on gaps between laboratory data and component SCALE
Kleinproben	Bruchmechanische Untersuchung von Reaktordruckbehälterstählen mittels Kleinprobentechnik
LTO	Long Term Operation
LWR	Light water reactor
MC(T)	Miniaturized Compact Tension
MEACTOS	Mitigating Environmentally-Assisted Cracking Through Optimisation of Surface Condition
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
PVP	Pressure Vessels & Piping
PWR	Pressurized Water Reactor
RPV	Reactor pressure vessel
SSTT	Small Specimen Test Techniques
STRUMAT-LTO	Structural Materials research for safe Long-Term Operation of LWR NPPs
VVER	Water-Water Energetic Reactor

1 Introduction

The FRACTESUS project aims to validate the usage of small-scale fracture toughness specimen testing for the safety assessment of reactor pressure vessels. The work undertaken in the project is aimed to convince appropriate authorities to use toughness data acquired from miniaturized compact tension specimens (MC(T)) in the Master Curve approach and finally introduce MC(T) specimens into surveillance programs.

To achieve this, the effect of specimen size on the fracture toughness properties needs to be studied. Finite element modelling (FEM) is used to investigate the difference between large-size and miniaturized compact tension specimens and to quantify the resulting loss of constraint due to the size reduction. As such, the optimal range of usability of MC(T) specimens can be determined and evidenced with experimental results. Large inter-laboratory testing is included in the FRACTESUS project to prove the repeatability and reproducibility of the small-scale testing of fracture toughness properties.

Fracture toughness on various materials (both base and welds) relevant for most of the available reactor materials and irradiation conditions are investigated. Because of this project, guidelines and standard practices will be composed for the use of MC(T) specimens in the Master Curve approach.

Part of the success of the present project relies on interactions with ongoing international activities: national and international activities related to long term operation of nuclear power plants; standardization bodies; academic and industrial professionals. The present deliverable summarizes the main interactions of the FRACTESUS project with international activities.

2 Description of international activities

2.1 EU supported projects

2.1.1 ENTENTE

“ENTENTE” is an EU-funded project aiming to design and implement a European Database for Multiscale Modelling of Radiation Damage. The project received funding from the EU-H2020-Euratom Research and Innovation Action under Grant Agreement No. 900018. The project runs for 4 years (09/2020 – 08/2024) with a budget of € 4M and involves 27 participants, coordinated by CIEMAT (Spain).

The overarching objective of the European Database for Multiscale Modelling of Radiation Damage (ENTENTE) project is to capitalize on past multiscale modelling projects, associated data acquisition projects and expert groups beyond national borders, to make modelling and experimental work on reactor pressure vessel (RPV) steel embrittlement converge and to reach an “entente” in terms of capturing the expansive knowledge on the relevant ageing phenomena. In this way, ENTENTE contributes to the improved safety of Nuclear Power Plants (NPPs) by enabling the development of quantitatively predictive and/or remediating tools or operational practices to support safe Long-Term Operation (LTO), not only for the existing nuclear fleet, but also for new light water reactors (Gen III/III+). The aim is to develop innovative data management tools to maximize access to and utilization of the results of the multiscale modelling and experimental programs. Such a database will improve upon the SOTERIA Platform, to test industrial reference cases, and to provide open access to this wealth of accumulated knowledge.

The literature data from large test specimens and the data acquired within FRACTESUS on MC(T) specimens from a wide range of RPV steels are suited to incorporation within the ENTENTE database in support of developing models for RPV embrittlement.

[<https://snetp.eu/portfolio-items/entente-2/>]

[<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/900018>]

2.1.2 STRUMAT-LTO

“STRUMAT-LTO” is an EU project involving Structural Materials research directed towards the safe Long-Term Operation of Light Water Reactor (LWR) NPPs. The project received funding from the EU-H2020-Euratom Research and Innovation Action under Grant Agreement No. 945272. The project runs for 4 years (09/2020 – 08/2024) with a budget of € 4.5M and involves 19 participants, coordinated by EK-CER (Hungary) and NRG (Netherlands).

One of the critical issues of LTO of, mainly, pressurized water reactors (PWRs) is the embrittlement of the RPV by neutron irradiation. Substantial research has been performed in various international collaborative research projects, such as LONGLIFE, PERFORM60, SOTERIA, etc., which have helped to improve the understanding of many open issues in RPV ageing phenomena, such as the effect of neutron flux and the influence of chemical/microstructural heterogeneities. Despite all the previous research on RPV embrittlement, however, there are several open issues, The STRUMAT-LTO project is aimed to address the remaining gaps and open issues in RPV embrittlement to support safe long-term operation of LWR NPPs, including the scenario of LTO > 60 years. A key open issue concerns whether embrittlement accelerates at high neutron fluences and the underlying mechanisms that would lead to accelerated embrittlement (i.e. formation of new phases or accelerated growth of existing clusters). STRUMAT-LTO is performing further research focusing on understanding the unfavorable synergy between Ni, Mn and Si on modifying the microstructure and mechanical properties of RPV steels at high fluences, to elucidate the late-onset irradiation effects. In addition, existing embrittlement trend equations (ETEs) tend to under predict RPV embrittlement at higher fluence regimes. Therefore, subsequent efforts are needed to validate/adapt the ETEs accordingly.

Finally, STRUMAT-LTO is investigating the applicability of the Master curve (MC) approach at high fluences the use of small/sub-sized specimens to characterize irradiation induced shifts in reference curves. In these, last two aspects, the synergy between FRACTESUS and STRUMAT-LTO is clear. Both projects expand the range of materials and irradiation conditions for which systematic investigation of MC(T) data acquisition and analysis is being investigated and insights developed from one project can inform the analysis of data from the other.

[<https://snetp.eu/portfolio-items/strumat-lto-2/>]

[<https://strumat-lto.eu>]

[<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/945272>]

2.1.3 DELISA-LTO

“DESLISA-LTO” is an EU-funded project studying the Description of the Extended Lifetime and its Influence on the Safety Operation and Construction Materials Performance – Long Term Operation with no

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2020-2024 under grant agreement No. 900014.

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Compromises in the Safety. The project received funding from the Horizon Euratom programme 2021 under grant agreement No 101061201. The project runs for 3 years (06/2022 – 09/2025) with a budget of € 3.3M and involves 8 participants coordinated by Centrum vyzkumu Rez (Czech Republic).

The aim of the project is to identify the components which are most degraded and threatened during long-term operation, to describe the effect of the LTO on the material properties and to develop a simulation tool able to predict when the component material reaches a non-acceptable state. The project is specifically focused on the Water-Water Energetic Reactor (VVER); nevertheless, the approach is intended to maintain easy transferability to other LWR technologies. The outputs of the project are intended to lead to the increase of operational safety at the extended lifetime due to the in-time prediction of the potential failure. The basic approach of the project is to combine the development of the simulation tools with experimental work (material analyses) and in-service and/or non-destructive inspection techniques to develop an effective “early warning” tool for the assessment of the system integrity. The project's aim specifically focuses on the thermal aging and swelling of loaded structural materials. Some of the components most degraded during LTO are the heat exchanger tubes of steam generators (experiencing thermal ageing) and the reactor internals (experiencing swelling). The material used for the DELIA-LTO experimental campaign was screened and selected according to the main criteria: to support and validate the proposed methods in the most accurate way; to be “on stock” and available at the expected start of the project. The experiments were planned to be performed on ex-service material with clear and well-described operational history as well as the material from the original batch in the “as-received” state to gain the most relevant and valuable information with high impact to the community.

Due to the constraints imposed by the component geometries, mechanical testing within DELISA-LTO will utilize a range of specimen geometries smaller than 0.5T compact tension samples. The applicability of data acquired within DELISA-LTO will be supported by the outcomes of FRACTESUS concerning best practice in the analysis of toughness data and will add to the population of data from 0.16TMC(T) and other geometries investigated within FRACTESUS.

[<https://delisa-lto.eu/>]

[<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/900018>]

2.1.4 INCEFA-SCALE

“INCEFA-SCALE” is an EU-funded project with the aim of INcreasing safety in NPPs by Covering gaps in Environmental Fatigue Assessment. It focusses on the gaps between laboratory data and the component SCALE. The project received funding from the EU-H2020-Euratom Research and Innovation Action under Grant Agreement No. 945300. The project runs for 5 years (10/2020 to 09/2025) with a budget of € 6.8M and involves 15 participants, coordinated by Jacobs Clean Energy Limited (UK).

The objective of the project is to advance the ability to predict lifetimes of Nuclear Plant components subjected to Environmental Assisted Fatigue loading. EPRI in the USA is leading a series of component scale environmental fatigue tests, which are expected to advance data availability significantly; however, ability to address transferability of laboratory scale tests to real component geometries and loadings will still be constrained by limited test data. This is the knowledge gap addressed by this project; it is recognized worldwide as significant.

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While there is no direct technical link with FRACTESUS in terms of data exchange or testing methodology, both projects aim to improve reactor safety, especially in view of LTO. The presentation of the key goals of both projects during seminars helps broadening the knowledge of the participants to these seminars, which is especially important to PhD students and early career scientists.

[<https://snetp.eu/portfolio-items/incefa-scale-2/>]

[<https://incefascale.unican.es/>]

[<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/945300>]

2.1.5 MEACTOS

MEACTOS” is an EU-funded project aiming to Mitigating Environmentally Assisted Cracking Through Optimization of Surface Condition. The project received funding from the EU-H2020-Euratom Research and Innovation Action under Grant Agreement No. 755151. The project ran for 4.5 years (09/2017 to 02/2022) with a budget of € 3.8M and involves 16 participants, led by CIEMAT (Spain).

The goal of the MEACTOS project is to improve the safety and reliability of Generation II and III nuclear power plants (NPPs) by improving the resistance of critical locations, including welds, to environmentally assisted cracking (EAC) through the application of optimized surface machining and improved surface treatments. This project will quantify the effect of various surface machining and treatment techniques on the EAC behavior of specific structural materials in the primary circuit of NPPs. The gained knowledge will be summarized in practical guidelines, which can be used for incorporation into key nuclear design and manufacturing codes. Furthermore, a tailored roadmap for harmonization of guidelines and codes will be produced. In these ways, MEACTOS will improve safe and reliable economic nuclear energy production in Europe. MEACTOS will contribute to tackling the obsolescence of the machining practices used in the nuclear field with direct application to the construction of the new plants.

While there is no direct technical link with FRACTESUS in terms of data exchange or testing methodology, both projects aim to improve reactor safety and exploitation economy. The joint paper written between the projects (including INCEFA-SCALE) and presentation at the SNETP Forum 2022 helps broadening the knowledge of the participants, which is especially important to PhD students and early career scientists.

[<https://meactos.eu/>]

[<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/755151>]

2.2 Other International activities

2.2.1 IAEA CRP on SSTT

Under the auspices of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), a Coordinated Research Project (CRP) titled “Towards the Standardization of Small Specimen Test Techniques for Fusion Applications” started in 2017. The overall objective of this project is to provide the bases for the standardization of SSTT specimens making them available for their use in Fusion material irradiation facilities. This includes: (a) to provide a set of guidelines for SSTT based on common agreed best practices on main test techniques (tensile, creep, low cycle fatigue, fracture toughness, fatigue crack growth) valid for reference structural Fusion materials (RAFM steels); (b) to establish supporting experimental activities and (c) to elaborate

datasets and elements needed for a full standardization of the SSTT by an international authority like ASTM or ISO.

As participants in this project, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) and the Centre for Energy, Environmental and Technological Research (CIEMAT) performed interlaboratory fracture toughness testing based on the Master Curve method in the ASTM E1921-21 standard. The tests were performed on RAFM steels EUROFER97 and F82H by using standard and small specimens (mini CT and mini TPB). Considering \pm one standard deviation ($\pm 1\sigma$), there was no obvious specimen size effect in 0.5 T C(T) and 4 mm MC(T) specimens on measured Master Curve reference temperature T_0 , while 1.65 mm bend bar specimens yielded a higher (more conservative) T0Q for both steels.

2.3 National projects

2.3.1 Kleinproben

Kleinproben" is a German national project investigating Fracture Mechanics Investigation of Reactor Pressure Vessel Steel by means of Sub-sized Specimen. The project received funding from the BMWi Reaktorsicherheitsforschung, Grant Agreement No. 1501592B. The project ran 3 years (2019-2022) and involves two German participants, namely, HZDR and FRA-G.

The project aimed to establish a procedure for fracture mechanics testing of neutron-irradiated reactor pressure vessel (RPV) steels using MC(T) specimens with respect to manufacturing of specimens, precracking, and measurement of the crack opening displacement / load line displacement. The project investigated specific fracture mechanics properties as a function of irradiation conditions to demonstrate the transferability of fracture mechanics data from MC(T) to standard Charpy-sized specimens. As a part of establishing such transferability, fracture surfaces were investigated to determine the location of fracture initiation sites and to determine the dominant fracture modes.

The Kleinproben and FRACTESUS projects have overlapped, so that insights gained within one project have informed the procedures utilized in the other, and the combined datasets support the statistical underpinning of the analyses of data from each project.

[<https://www.hzdr.de/publications/Publ-36701>]

2.4 Conference Sessions

2.4.1 ASME Pressure Vessel & Piping Conference

The Pressure Vessels & Piping (PVP) Conference is an annual event that brings together engineers, researchers, and industry professionals from around the world to discuss the latest advancements in the fields of pressure vessels, piping, and related technologies. Organized by the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME), this conference serves as a key platform for the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and best practices in the design, analysis, manufacturing, and operation of pressure vessels and piping systems.

During the 2023 and 2024 meetings, special sessions (two in 2023 and one in 2024) specifically dedicated to the FRACTESUS project were organized by Mark Kirk, Masato Yamamoto and William Server under the umbrella of the PVP Codes & Standards Committee activities, which also gathered contributions from

some of the projects described above, providing an excellent context of scientific and technical discussion on LTO activities and miniature specimen characterization.

3 Activities Summary

The table below summarizes the main interactions of the FRACTESUS project with other international activities.

Date	Event	Description
8 Feb. 2022	FRACTESUS 4th Executive Committee Meeting Virtual, Teams	The STRUMAT-LTO project was presented to the FRACTESUS ExCom members. Return of experience on MC(T) testing in FRACTESUS and fracture toughness data from STRUMAT-LTO could be exchanged. Also a common session on the PVP2024 and participation in each other's workshops/seminars was agreed.
8 – 9 Nov. 2022	FRACTESUS half-yearly progress meeting Lakehouse Auditorium 2 Mol, Belgium	The KleinProben project was presented to the FRACTESUS participants. The data obtained from the KleinProben project is available to the FRACTESUS project.
15 Dec. 2022	Overview article in EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.	An overview of the FRACTESUS, INCEFA-SCALE and MEACTOS projects were jointly presented in the article EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol. 8 (2022) 42 (2022), https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2022033
22 Feb. 2023	FRACTESUS 6th Executive Committee Meeting Virtual, Teams	The DELISA-LTO project as well as some technical highlights were presented to the FRACTESUS ExCom members. The scientific approaches and techniques are similar in both projects. Fracture toughness data on 0.5T-C(T) specimens from DELISA-LTO can be shared with FRACTESUS. Participation in each other's workshops/seminars was agreed.
1 Jun. 2023	ENTENTE Exploitation team meeting Virtual, Zoom	The FRACTESUS project was presented during the ENTENTE Exploitation team meeting. During the discussion it was agreed that the FRACTESUS data will be formatted allowing for an easy integration into the ENTENTE database.
6 Jun. 2023	DELISA-LTO 1st yearly meeting Virtual, Zoom	The FRACTESUS project was presented during the DELISA-LTO 1 st yearly meeting. The scientific approaches and techniques are similar in both projects. Fracture toughness data on 0.5T-C(T) specimens from DELISA-LTO can be shared with FRACTESUS. Participation in each other's workshops/seminars was agreed.

7 Jun. 2023	<p>FRACTESUS half-yearly progress meeting Virtual, Teams</p>	<p>The DELISA-LTO project as well as some technical highlights were presented to the FRACTESUS participants. The scientific approaches and techniques are similar in both projects. Fracture toughness data on 0.5T-C(T) specimens from DELISA-LTO can be shared with FRACTESUS. Participation in each other's workshops/seminars was agreed.</p>
16 Jul. – 21 Aug. 2023	<p>ASME PVP 2023 Westin Peachtree Plaza Atlanta, GA, USA</p>	<p>Presentation of the FRACTESUS project and presentations related to FRACTESUS results were provided during two special sessions. A total 7 FRACTESUS related papers were published.</p>
19 – 20 Sep. 2023	<p>INCEFA-SCALE Mid-term Seminar Parainfo de la Universidad de Cantabria, c/ Sevilla 6 Santader, Spain</p>	<p>The FRACTESUS project was presented during the INCEFA-SCALE Mid-term seminar. The seminar/workshop was aimed at PhD students; professional engineers and researchers working in the fields of fatigue, environmental fatigue or structural integrity; highly experienced researchers and engineers wishing to update their knowledge and share experiences.</p>
12 – 13 Dec. 2023	<p>FRACTESUS half-yearly progress meeting Lakehouse Auditorium 2 Mol, Belgium</p>	<p>The latest news of the ASTM committee E08.07 on ASTM standards E1921 and E1820 was presented to the FRACTESUS participants. A call for support was launched to the FRACTESUS participants was launched to potentially relax the crack size variation requirements in section 8.6.3 of ASTM E1921</p>
28-30 May 2024	<p>STRUMAT-LTO Summer School ÚJV Řež, 130 Hlavní 250 68 Husinec Czech Republic</p>	<p>The FRACTESUS project and its main advances were presented during the STRUMAT-LTO Summer School. The event aimed to ensure the transfer of knowledge between retiring and new members of the nuclear workforce. In a conference format, several nuclear experts presented the latest results and findings of STRUMAT-LTO and other sister projects such as ENTENTE, FRACTESUS and DELISA, followed by a series of expert lectures.</p>
28 Jul. – 2 Aug. 2024	<p>ASME PVP 2024 Hyatt Regency Bellevue Bellevue, WA, USA</p>	<p>Presentation of the FRACTESUS project and presentations related to FRACTESUS results were provided during one special session. An additional contribution from FRACTESUS consortium was presented in an additional session dedicated to small-scale testing. A total 5 FRACTESUS related papers were published.</p>

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10 – 11 Sep. 2024	FRACTESUS final seminar Parainfo de la Universidad de Cantabria, c/ Sevilla 6 Santader, Spain	The main results of the projects KleinProben , INCEFA-SCALE , STRUMAT-LTO and ENTENTE will be presented during the FRACTESUS final seminar.
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4 Conclusion

Throughout the execution of the FRACTESUS project, frequent interactions with other ongoing international activities took place. During special seminars and project meetings, the projects KleinProben, MEACTOS, ENTENTE, INCEFA-SCALE, STRUMAT-LTO and DELISA LTO were presented to the FRACTESUS participants and vice versa. As a result, return of experience as well as mechanical data could be exchanged. Additional interactions with international academic and industrial professionals took place during dedicated FRACTESUS sessions at the ASME Pressure Vessel & Piping Conference.

